

PAKISTAN'S ROLE IN AFGHANISTAN'S RECONSTRUCTION AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17205354>

Keywords

Pakistan, Afghanistan, Education, Health, Political Transition

Article History

Received: 01 July 2025

Accepted: 11 September 2025

Published: 26 September 2025

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Abstract

Afghanistan had been in a state of conflict for over four decades. Apart from human and capital losses, these battles have harmed the region's social infrastructure. Social sectors like health, education, roads, bridges, power plants, and telecommunications have all suffered significant damage. Kabul, Afghanistan's capital, was destroyed, and the country's governmental system was severely harmed. Millions of Afghan refugees have been compelled to seek asylum in neighboring countries, most notably Pakistan, which has the longest porous border with Afghanistan. The goal of this study is to showcase Pakistan's efforts and financial assistance for Afghanistan's social rebuilding in the post-9/11 era. Afghanistan, which is gradually rising from decades of conflict and destruction, needs the special attention of major powers and neighboring nations, notably Pakistan, to revitalize and reconstruct what it has lost over the years. Pakistan has played an important role in Afghanistan's rehabilitation. Over the last 15 years, it has supported several sectors in Afghanistan, including communication, education, health, and banking, to boost economic growth in the war-torn country and aid in the restoration of peace and security in the area. Aside from physical restoration, Pakistan has employed a soft power strategy, investing in capacity building and technical training programs. Soft power refers to the peaceful resolution of disputes and the expansion of economic cooperation. In this age of globalization, the use of soft power over armed methods is gaining traction. The main goal of Pakistan's soft power policy has been to win over Afghan sentiments and establish a thriving civil society in Afghanistan. This circumstance would pave the way for the eradication of extremism, militancy, and terrorism, as well as alter the nature of Pakistan-Afghan ties. The major goal of this study is to show Pakistan's contribution to Afghanistan's societal rebuilding. The secondary sources are used to collect data for study. The qualitative approach is used for this study.

INTRODUCTION

Faith is very important if there is no essential component for cooperation. It is the duty of every state that if it wants to maintain Trading of Afghanistan is occurred largely through Pakistan and Afghanistan is the third on the list of exporters of Pakistan and has the benefit of trading formally as well as informally 4 billion dollars annually. While there are two billion dollars annually is through legal between these countries. The things exported in Afghanistan are encouraged by Afghan people as the demand for Pakistani goods and it can be assured as the refugees going back to Afghanistan used to say all this. For example, the medicines issued by Pakistan are slightly more costly than Indian medicines. However, the trade route through Pakistan is the central point of the economy of Afghanistan, and Pakistan's access to the Central Asian Republics is a long-ranging benefit for Pakistan. Though, Afghanistan is a country that is passing through a difficult time and is wanting to be explored and considerable efforts are being made. This country is full of natural sources like the ores of iron and copper as well as the resources of oil, coal, gas, and some type of gemstones as well (Durani & Khan, 2009).

In Afghanistan natural gas has deposits of 1.6 trillion cubic feet, oil reserves include 95 million barrels and coal has 400 MT which is given to Pakistan to meet its energy needs. With the improvement of political issues in Afghanistan, trading can go on to its peak because of the availability of routes by Pakistan. According to a 2017 survey, Pakistan has a population of 197 million and the percentage of working people is 53 percent it has been seen that the persons above 20 are doing their job and want to have better job facilities. Pakistan is not in a state to remain stuck to giving job opportunities to the young generation, it has to promote its relations with neighboring countries like China, Afghanistan, Iran, and CARs for trading. Pakistan can issue jobs by making zones around the border for economic building and through the use of people-to-people interactions it can be promoted. Pakistan's aid to the Taliban and then for insurgency for the interests can overcome the confusion by giving interdependency over-trading and in this way, stability as well as peace can be brought in this region.

Afghanistan is a landlocked country consisting of dry and stony places and is almost the size of Texas. It had faced the events of the war for three decades and its economic structure is fully devastated rurally as well as urbanely. Its administration also lacks the law-and-order situation and the security concerns are part of the country. Afghanistan is on the page of reconstruction, making understanding with countries, the makeup of civil societies, and its construction of state institutions and keeping services to the people in providing job availabilities. Pakistan is its neighboring country and could be a partner in its projects making jolly relations.

These two countries can have benefits together as they are connected socially and make peace in the region by completing the recovery mode in Afghanistan. The time after the Taliban has provided better opportunities to integrate and cooperate between Central Asia and South Asia. There is a need for investment by Pakistan in many areas including education, healthiness, natural gas ducts, electric transmission, and reconstruction of roads, hospitals, bridges, and tunnels under the mountain. These reforms would able both nations to have long stability in their relations and the region as well. The people-to-people scenario can increase cooperation if its focus is boosted. Many people in both states have given their interviews about building trust and the need for cooperation to sort out the problems. They are in the argument that if the trade is made possible and the cooperation in security, water, and business is present then lack of trust can be undone easily.

This study deals with future relations based on construction purposes in Afghanistan. This material provides information about the era after the Taliban. There has been search on which progress can be made to increase relations. This also discusses the culture, education, and economic conditions of both countries and has mentioned the specific components for the development of trust which was lost in war. This covers the political situation that changed after the Taliban's era.

Material and Methods

The funding systems are also a concern in reconstructing the infrastructure. Evaluation of economic, security, and diplomatic strategies are in

this context as well. The extent of cooperation between Pakistan and Afghanistan has been in the study and the projects on which the trust can be built are of the view. There are other things like Afghanistan's access to the Gwadar port, Pakistan's access to the CARs, Afghanistan's step in SAARC and ECO, and Pakistan's part in Afghanistan that have been stressed. To understand the Pakistan's role in development of Afghanistan, this study adopted analytical and descriptive designs. The data for the article is collected from secondary sources which includes newspapers, books, journals, and previous research works. The qualitative approach is used for this study.

Soft power Theory

This study relates to the soft power theory for a reason, Pakistan-Afghanistan ties might be altered by prioritizing diplomacy, trade, and technology over threats and intimidation. Soft power is a different strategy for dealing with militancy and extremism. If hard power may aid in the resolution of an issue by coercive and military measures, soft power can reduce the use of force and other punishing techniques in a conflict scenario through the use of noncoercive means. Joseph Nye's soft power theory (Ahamr, 2021).

Pakistan is assisting Afghanistan with social, human, political, and infrastructure development. Pakistan's Ambassador to Afghanistan stated in his statement at the inauguration of Jinnah Hospital in Kabul that Pakistan's bilateral development contribution had surpassed one billion US dollars in 2019. He went on to say that Pakistan is providing this assistance to Afghanistan in order to build and extend people-to-people ties between the two nations (News, 2019). The development funding is being utilized in a variety of programs involving infrastructure, education, health, agriculture, and the capacity building of Afghan professionals (Easterly, 2021). The aid made a considerable contribution to Afghan state-building, but it was unable to produce a favorable image for Pakistan (Ullah & Gohar, 2020). However, cooperation then it should collaborate over joint defection as well. It is thought that mutual collaboration lay the foundation of advantages to a lot but there are some scholars such as Karen Cooke and Russell Hardin Levi have faith that trust is not

important for teamwork because it is not only maintained but can be increased by institutional reforms (Cook, Levi, & Hardin, 2005). Instead of having issues due to mistrust, there are bilateral relations in the way of trading and Pakistan's involvement in the reconstruction of institutions, which shows the cooperation at this level. When there are interactions at large, then positivity can be seen in economic interdependency and an impression is left on the government (Usman, Ghufraan, & Majeed, 2016).

Pakistani Support towards Political Transition and Afghanistan's Reconstruction

After the entering of Pakistan in the Bonn conference, changes occurred in the politics as well as in the constitutional way making the basics of their relations. The talks were finished with the agreement having provisional measures while pending the Re-establishment of Permanent Government institutions consisting of three principal manuscripts and three extensions and it was recognized the day by the United Nations Security Council in perseverance. Pakistan described the Bonn Conference as a favor in the efforts laid by the Afghan people. Pakistan's foreign minister, Aziz Ahmad Khan, said that Pakistan had faced many costs economically as well as socially just as the outcome of the conflicts around Afghanistan.

Hamid Karzai remained in the transitional authority by obtaining support from delegations in the Loya Jirga. The commission consisting of 35 members traveled around the country to have consultancies with Afghan people. The Loya Jirga presented the constitution and it was decided that the elections were carried on. There were many reasons then for postponing the elections but later on, Hamid Karzai was made the first democratically elected president of Afghanistan. He had many issues with the administration of the country as there was the reconstruction of the infrastructure, justice problems, human violations, democracy, issues of refugees, and the social norms rehabilitation. The elections were taken place on time end up people crossing the border were involved because of Pakistan it made sure the MOU among the refugees, so they took part in the presidential elections. And it was seen that there were no attacks during that

whole process. Pakistan made available the full check and balance in the election areas among refugees so that no calamity would take place.

By signing the Bonn agreement Afghanistan made itself available internationally but there are some points that are responsible for the negative impact as well. The first and the leading cause was the absence of the Taliban and the Mujahedeen and among them, some participated in making the vital government. On one side Bonn agreement made sure stability for a short while but on the other hand Taliban grew because they were not fully abolished. Abdul Rashid Dostum, Abdul Rab Rasool Sayyaf, and Ismail Khan were the warlords who supported the Karzai Government and were not interested in strengthening its government. They were interested in their position in the governing areas which weakened the relations as well as the Bonn goals. The USA had believed after the Bonn conference that Afghanistan would soon be a democratic country through international support. Then the Iraq fight damaged the stability in Afghanistan a lot and attention was moved to this point (Waqas et al., 2019).

Another thing which deteriorated the strength of government was the United Nations resolution which made the Al-Qaida and Taliban on the same page and sanctions were forced upon them. This Taliban movement was native as it had the local population which had tired of previous wars. It was suggested that many afghan people who were educated might have infuriated with non-Pashtuns equally, but it proved blessings for the rural areas because they had faced hardships from the Afghan wars. The sanctions applied on the Taliban isolated them and blocked the way of settlement. Mullah Omer and Jalal Uddin Haqqani reorganized the movement and the only goal was to destabilize the Karzai government.

Pakistan's Role in Afghanistan's infrastructure Development

Soviets and then with the Taliban, etc. These things have damaged Afghanistan a lot and destroyed the infrastructure. Pakistan is playing its role in the reconstruction business and in the stability of the state and prosperity as well which will reduce the gap between them which is a very good sign to come

closer. It was an essential element for the government of Karzai to build the damaged part of the country as a result of the war. Then there was the issue of security especially for those who were rebuilding the city.

The role of Pakistan is very illustrative because it is nearer and the neighbor next to it. There was a fund which collected internationally as the first conference on the topic of the reconstruction of Afghanistan. The primary function of the conference was to access need-based assessment funds for reconstruction. UNDP as well as the World Bank estimated that Afghanistan needs 1.7 Billion Dollars for one year, then 10 Billion Dollars for the next 5 years, and 15 Billion Dollars for the next 10 years. Some analysts relating to politics have suggested that the total amount which is needed to rebuild Afghanistan is Thirty Billion Dollars. The conference assured the 1.8 Billion Dollars against the amount set as 1.7 Billion Dollars and facilitated the others like UN agencies, rehabilitation organizations, and Provisional authorities to start their work regularly. This conference held in Tokyo funded a lot in the consistency of Afghanistan (Carothers, 2007). There were sixty-two nations across the world and the donors have twenty-one generations as well. Among them, some made promises for years for funding. While some of them gave support not considering the monetary values.

All the organizations as a whole decided to help the torn country to reconstruct. Both the Bonn and Tokyo conference showed some hope that the country would soon be in the line of peaceful countries which have well-organized systems, the value of democracy, and reconstruction businesses. And doing all that Afghanistan would get relief from the miseries led by wars. The rebuilding of Afghanistan's torn pieces, the main aim, was started at large but the element of the piece couldn't be brought to the state because of the security concerns in this region.

In Tokyo, Pakistan donated 100 million US dollars for the restoration process of Afghanistan, and it was a positive sign in bringing the softness of the relations between these two countries. Pakistan next time gave the double as two hundred US dollars for the betterment of the benevolent sphere (Adeney, 2008). According to Pakistan's perspective,

Afghanistan got facilities while Pakistan has shared the burden of restoration, and the field which benefitted are; trade, health, education, construction, banking, the agricultural field, and industry. The different fields such as the Banking sector, Medicinal industry, Constructing & Material making industry have been expanded by the investment by Pakistan.

Pakistan decided to fight against terrorism by remaining on the front line, and it will make sure the involvement in the reconstruction of the torn pieces like in the field of educational institutes, hospitals infrastructure, and communication substructure, and this the peace would be maintained which will govern trade possibility and economy conditions would stable. On the other hand, the commercial happenings will be expanded in this region.

To gain control once again, Pakistan made thinking to use soft power, which is the use of a peaceful way of decreasing conflicts and enhancing the economy of the country, by investing in the educational field, health-related packages, technical pieces of training, and capability constructing programs. Regarding military aspects, the value of soft power has increased a lot in the current world for their interests. Pakistan's main objective in doing so was to change the thinking of the common people, to have good thinking in building a lively civil society which will, in turn, build social as well as cultural bridges to give the relations a new nature between Pakistan and Afghanistan. In doing so the common people would contribute to lowering the militancy in this region and providing stability with peace as well. The swelling progression in the Department of Transport was an important step in building strong relations based on trade between Pakistan and Afghanistan.

The trade between Kabul and Islamabad has huge benefits in the long range because it can increase the profits of the government, provide jobs for the young generation of Afghanistan, and the growth progress. This progress will increase if the communication gaps are filled and the interactions are reached to its limit. Recently, it has been noted that the transportation infrastructure should be the focus of restoration because the expensive route needed to be inexpensive to expand the connectivity between the two countries. Furthermore, the development in the

region will prosper, refugee problems will be solved, and economic growth will upsurge. The world report on the trade of Afghanistan with other countries has revealed that developing countries have a poor system of transportation and lower grade logistic system then the cost will be high, and the sale prices increases by 50% more than the previous value as you can see on the grains. Afghanistan's infrastructure for transport was not developed and it was tattered for about two decades. So, there was an extreme need in Afghanistan for transport development so that the cost would be less for traveling and trade revenue build-up systems would develop (Ahmed & Bhatnagar, 2015). Pakistan's related construction businesses were Health, Capacity building programs, Education systems, and Communication.

Pakistani role in Communication sector

Afghanistan's communication system has deteriorated during the last few decades. The aircraft bombing of Russian forces damaged a large chunk of the telecom infrastructure throughout the 1980s. Pakistan is now paying attention to manage road associations, and communication better, and restructuring the pieces of materials to encourage trade between Afghanistan and CARs to cover the whole region. 27.34 Billion Rupees has been suggested for the building of main highways which would connect the region together under the projects of infrastructure makeup. The road of Torkham-to-Jalabad is the central key point to discuss because it is that point which connects the two countries and also links Pakistan with the Central Asian Republics for successful trade. It is an important step by Pakistan to develop strong relations with Afghanistan producing trust and coordination in this region. \$34.42 Million the amount of 250 million dollars which was suggested for Afghanistan by Pakistan for the next five years (Carothers, 2007)

The double lane was made by FWO (Frontier Works Organization), part of Pakistan's army. This project initiated the bus service and traveling form Jalalabad to Torkham was started which is not a regrettable point in the development process. Then Pakistan started its national trade corridor with its neighboring countries including Afghanistan and CARs. Chaman-Spin Boldak Rail connection was

made for the cost of twelve million dollars as agreed between these two countries. An MOU was signed between Pakistan Railway and a team from Afghanistan headed by Deputy Minister. This MOU was prepared by the Pakistan railway as well. Pakistan railways were asked to stop for a while because of some procedures to carry on. Two projects on roads in Jalalabad having the length of 32 Km and 25 Km have been accomplished. These kinds of projects will not only link the two cities together but will accumulate the stability factor as well. However, Pakistan has provided different types of road construction machinery to facilitate the construction works in Nangarhar, Kandahar, and various other provinces of Afghanistan.

Pakistani Support in Health Sector

The health sector is the most important indicator in the development of the country. The situation of hospitals is at its frightening peak as there are very few hospitals in Afghanistan. There was a need to invest in this category and Pakistan did as Afghans are giving free treatment in government hospitals. 40% of the patient in Peshawar hospitals are from Afghanistan and 50% in Quetta fill out the form. So, we can say that almost 90% of the Afghans come to Pakistan for treatment. Pakistan built Jinnah Hospital in Kabul consisting of 150 beds and a Thalassemia center as well with the cost of 1200 million Pakistani rupees. 25-acre land was provided by the Afghan government as assistance.

In the summer of 2010, Nishtar Kidney Centre was finalized in Jalalabad having the price of the project being 395 million Pakistani rupees. Doctors and the other medical staff took training in Pakistan. Zia-ul-Haq Artificial Limb Center (Badakhshan), 50-bed Al-Shifa Eye Hospital (Gardez), Syed Ahmed Shaheed Hospital, 50-bed Al-Shifa eye hospital (Kunduz), and 200-bed Naib Amanullah Khan Hospital (Logar) are some of the beneficent works under the process of completion. Dispensaries all over Afghanistan are another decision by Pakistan for which the government has provided funds. On the other hand, Pakistan has the ability to change the insurgency in the opposite direction to save the future of Afghanistan people as well as the economy enhancement programs (Ahmed & Bhatnagar, 2015).

Nowadays, social security is involved in the upsurge of cooperation between the countries. In this scenario, Pakistan is establishing social security to enable the common man to have access to the basic facilities of education and health and would enable to change the perception of these people about Pakistan as an aggressive and hard-handed country.

Pakistani Role in Education Department

It is a vital element in the development of the country and is the basic need of the common man as well. It is the backbone of the solidification of relations through peace and understanding. Pakistan wants men and women in Afghanistan to get an education from Basic to Higher. In Kabul, Allama Iqbal Faculty of Arts was established with a construction cost of 411.256 million rupees. In Mazar-I-Sharif, Balkh University, Liaquat Ali Khan Engineering Faculty Block was prepared for better education for the worth of 600 million rupees. Rehman Baba School was renewed in Kabul at the cost of two million rupees. 2,800 modern computers, 300,000 kits for students, and 2,000 scholarships were awarded to have Higher Education in Afghanistan. Furthermore, 28,000 Afghan students had been cultured from Pakistani educational institutes, 6,000 are getting into different institutions and about 50,000 children from Afghan refugees are in the school systems in Pakistan. Afghans who have completed graduation from Pakistan are getting good salaries in Afghanistan. They are at high levels in offices, organizations, and different NGOs. The government of Afghan has allowed different NGOs to build schools here based on Afghan criteria. About 428 primary & high schools are functional in different cities in Pakistan (Usman, Ghufuran, & Majeed, 2016).

In establishing strong relations based on the education department, long time cooperation can be built. If anyone wants to know the statistics of bilateral relations between Pakistan and Afghanistan, one should know the security, diplomatic and economic conditions after the Taliban era. In this way, dares about their bilateral relations and the consequences of future cooperation can be clarified.

Conclusion

Although the situations are very critical on both sides, they have some common points also and want to stable their bilateral relations as well. Pakistan has taken steps with respect to this agenda and is helping Afghanistan in rebuilding the construction of torn pieces of the building. Pakistan has invested in many aspects like the construction of the road from Torkham to Jalalabad and the formation of Jinnah Hospital Complex, Kabul, and the Allam Iqbal Faculty of Arts at the University at Kabul. Pakistan has also offered scholarships for many students of Afghanistan as well. Pakistan has provided facilities to Afghanistan as it is a landlocked country and Pakistan provides the nearest trade transit through seaport. Afghanistan is the third on the list among which countries to which Pakistan exports so in this way it is the best option for Pakistan to trade with its neighboring country and both countries will be benefitted from this session. Pakistan has enthusiastic feelings about the new project linking the South Asian states and it has the name of Turkmenistan-Afghanistan-Pakistan-India pipeline. This project will not only increase the relations with Pakistan on better values but also America will focus on Afghanistan as its energy areas availability and will win the confidence of America. The hurdle in the fulfillment of the peace in this region is not through bilateral relations. TAPI pipeline will make Pakistan an independent state in regard to the energy doles from the states of the Middle East. Doing this project will enable the other central Asian republics as well as Afghanistan itself to be the recipient for other members of the project as well. They need to cooperate to a large so that mega projects would not back up by superpowers. If there are developmental projects and the wishes of the countries are considered, then both can decrease the differences. If there is sharing of the cost and the welfare of the projects operated in both states, then policymakers can understand the availability of peace on both sides and the reasons will be collected for better cooperation. If there is a converging of the economic benefits, then mutual collaboration, as well as economic strength, can be increased. When both countries will start to understand their dependency on each other for their progress then political

strength will also be governed by their mutual support.

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